

SPEG gene mutation: a rare variant of centronuclear myopathy

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ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION: Centronuclear myopathies (CNM) are congenital myopathies characterised by clinical and genetic diversity, marked by elevated central nuclei and type I myofiber atrophy.

Centronuclear myopathy manifests as hypotonia, limb weakness, and a progressive course. The pathogenic gene, recently identified as striated preferentially expressed gene (SPEG), remains poorly understood, with limited reports on SPEG mutations. This study introduces a novel SPEG mutation, aiming to enhance understanding, expand the SPEG gene spectrum, and contribute to early diagnosis and genetic counselling.

CASE REPORT: A 4.5-year-old female presented to the clinic with a 1 year-long history of weakness in both lower extremities, along with easy fatigue, an unstable gait, frequent falls while walking, challenges standing up after falling or squatting, and difficulty climbing stairs. Running and jumping became impossible, initially unnoticed by the family but gradually worsening over time. The patient exhibited delayed motor development from childhood. Genetic sequencing identified SPEG gene mutations in the child, specifically c.4216C>G p.Pro1406Ala, a homozygous variant on Exon 17. **DISCUSSION:** The SPEG gene, located on chromosome 2q35, encodes SPEG, a crucial protein for muscle cell skeleton formation. SPEG's interaction with MTM1 disrupts Ca²⁺ homeostasis, influencing muscle cell development. Four SPEG subtypes (SPEG α , SPEG β , APEG-1, BPEG) exhibit tissue-specific expression, impacting clinical phenotypes. Treatment approaches lack uniformity, with ongoing research exploring cellular, molecular, and genetic-level interventions. **CONCLUSION:** This study adds to the diversity of Centronuclear myopathy cases by introducing a unique SPEG mutation, emphasizing varied clinical manifestations. Insights gained contribute to the understanding of SPEG gene mutations, offering valuable guidance for prenatal diagnosis and genetic counseling in managing individuals with congenital myopathies.

INTRODUCTION

Centronuclear myopathies (CNM) encompass a range of congenital myopathies characterized by clinical and genetic diversity. Termed for the elevated central nuclei in myofibers, coupled with type I myofiber atrophy evident in muscle biopsies, these conditions were initially documented by Spiro et al. in 1966^[1]. Clinical presentations typically involve hypotonia, limb weakness, drooping eyelids, extraocular muscle paralysis, and a gradually progressive course. The pathogenic gene is identified in 60–80% of CNM cases, with the recent discovery of a novel pathogenic gene, the striated preferentially expressed gene (SPEG). Presently, there are limited reports on SPEG mutations. Our study reveals a unique mutation in SPEG, previously unreported. By presenting the data of a child with Centronuclear myopathy resulting from SPEG gene mutation, this study aims to enhance clinician's comprehension of the disorder, broaden the SPEG gene spectrum, and contribute to early diagnosis and genetic counselling for affected individuals.

CASE REPORT

A 4.5-year-old female presented to the clinic with a 1 year-long history of weakness in both lower extremities, along with easy fatigue, an unstable gait, frequent falls while walking, challenges standing up after falling or squatting, and difficulty climbing stairs. Running and jumping became impossible, initially unnoticed by the family but gradually worsening over time. The patient exhibited delayed motor development from childhood, achieving head control at 3 months, sitting at 10 months, and walking at 2 years. Intellectual development remained normal before and after symptom onset. Born naturally at term to healthy parents with no consanguinity, the patient's 11-year-old sister also displayed similar childhood muscle weakness.

The patient maintained clear consciousness and good orientation; however, she could only speak in bisyllables. Physical examinations revealed dysmorphic facial features with normal pulmonary and abdominal findings, but grade -3 systolic murmur on auscultation at left upper sternal border and a history of frequent respiratory infections and failure to gain weight. Serum creatine kinase levels were within normal range. Electromyography (EMG) revealed myogenic damage changes with mild neurogenic damage changes, while echocardiography showed atrial septal defect of 16 x 18 mm ostium secundum type with dilated right atrium and ventricles. The MRI Brain was suggestive of atrophic changes in the fronto-parietal and temporal lobes(FIG.1, 2, 3), while EEG was normal. Genetic sequencing identified SPEG gene mutations in the child, specifically c.4216C>G p.Pro1406Ala, a homozygous variant on Exon 17 .

The patient was started on oral combination of spirinolactone and furosemide along with amino acid supplements and multivitamins. She was started with limb physiotherapy and speech therapy while her surgical correction of atrial septal defect was planned. Her parents were also counselled for genetic counselling for planning future pregnancies.

FIG.1.

FIG.2.

FIG.3.

DISCUSSION:

CNM categorization includes the following types: 1) X-linked recessive myotubular myopathy, attributed to the MTM1 gene encoding the MTM1 protein. It represents the most severe CNM subtype, with most affected males succumbing to respiratory failure before age 1. Survival into childhood or adolescence is rare. Female MTM1 heterozygous carriers may also manifest the disease, possibly linked to nonrandom X chromosome inactivation. 2) Autosomal dominant types involve DNM2, CCDC78, BIN1, and MTMR14 genes, exhibiting a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations. 3) Autosomal recessive types are associated with RYR1, TTN, and SPEG genes, displaying moderate to severe clinical phenotypes [2,3,4,5,6,7,8].

In 2014, Agrawal PB et al. first reported three cases of SPEG gene mutation, establishing its association with CNM [9]. Subsequently, 11 SPEG-related CNM cases have been reported. The SPEG gene, located on chromosome 2q35 with 51 exons, encodes striated muscle preferentially expressed protein kinase (SPEG), crucial for muscle cell skeleton formation. Current research suggests that SPEG, a molecular partner of MTM1, interacts with MTM1, disrupting Ca²⁺ homeostasis in the sarcoplasmic reticulum and affecting nucleus positioning during muscle maturation. This leads to abnormal muscle cell skeleton development. Murine models identified four SPEG subtypes (SPEG α , SPEG β , APEG-1, and BPEG), with tissue-specific expression influencing clinical phenotypes [10,11,12].

Among the 11 reported SPEG-associated CNM patients, there were 4 males and 7 females, including a pair of fraternal twin sisters from China. Onset occurred in the neonatal or infantile periods, with 4 cases succumbing within 3 weeks after birth and 1 at 19 weeks. Clinical symptoms mirrored general CNM cases: hypotonia, delayed motor milestones, muscle weakness or atrophy, weak sucking or chewing, ophthalmoplegia, blepharoptosis, and severe respiratory muscle involvement requiring postpartum mechanical ventilation support. Physical examination revealed malformations like high palatine arch, scoliosis, joint contracture, flat or arched feet, pectus excavatum, and posterior mandible contraction. Cardiac involvement was prominent, primarily dilated cardiomyopathy, and mitral or tricuspid valve insufficiency. Notably, a 10-year-old patient reported in 2018 did not develop cardiomyopathy [14], and another patient, reported by Wang H, exhibited axon neuropathy and myocardial densification insufficiency alongside CNM symptoms [13]. The child in this study, aged 13, showed no cardiac abnormalities on ultrasound, confirming that SPEG-related CNM might not always involve cardiomyopathy. The electromyogram (EMG) indicated mild neurogenic damage of the common

peroneal nerve, consistent with Wang H's report. The occurrence of cardiomyopathy may be linked to different SPEG gene mutation sites or variations in SPEG subtype expression in skeletal muscle and myocardium.

Presently, the treatment for CNM lacks uniformity. Cellular, molecular, and genetic-level treatment options are under investigation^[15]. Symptomatic approaches, such as feeding support, rehabilitation training, drug treatment for heart involvement, and surgery, are commonly recommended^[16]. While genotype-phenotype correlation remains unclear due to limited reported cases, ongoing research may unveil insights in the future. Nine of 11 patients underwent muscle biopsies, revealing common pathological features of increased myofibers with central nuclei and type I myofiber dysplasia predominance. This study contributes to the CNM case pool and expands the SPEG gene mutation spectrum, offering insights for prenatal diagnosis and genetic counseling.

CONCLUSION:

Distinct clinical manifestations exist in CNM patients due to varying SPEG gene mutation sites. This particular case included an atrial septal defect. Significantly, this research contributes to the diversity of CNM cases and widens the understanding of SPEG gene mutations, serving as a valuable resource for prenatal diagnosis and genetic counseling, thereby aiding healthcare professionals in managing and advising individuals affected by congenital myopathies.

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